

Synthesis of 6-(4'-keto-2'-cyclohexenyl)-2-methylheptane

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Methylheptanone on reduction with LiAlH_4 and iodination afforded 2-iodo-6-methylheptane, b.p. $68^\circ/7$ mm, which on subsequent condensation with diethyl malonate produced 2,6-dimethylheptane-1,1-dicarboxylate (I), b.p. $140-42^\circ/11$ mm. The di-ester (I) was treated with the methiodide of 4-diethylaminobutan-2-one, following Bardhan *et al.*, and the product on hydrolysis, decarboxylation, and esterification furnished ethyl 2-(butan-3'-one)-3,7-dimethyloctanoate (II).

The ester (II) on treatment with sodium hydride² yielded the dihydroresorcinol derivative (III) as a viscous oil. The mono-isobutyl ether of the diketone (III), b.p. $165-67^\circ/5$ mm, prepared in the usual way³, was reduced with LiAlH_4 and on subsequent treatment

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 3195.

2. *Organic Reactions*, John Wiley, New York, 1954, Vol. VIII, p. 126.

3. Frank and Hall, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 1645; Seifert and Schinz, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1951, **34**, 728.

with acid afforded the desired α β -unsaturated ketone (IV), b.p. 130-32°/5 mm, yielding a semicarbazone (m.p. 150.5°) and a 2,4-D.N.P. derivative (m.p. 113-14°). The ultraviolet absorption spectra of the present ketone (IV) ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 227 and 322 m μ ; log ϵ , 4.18 and 1.57 respectively) closely resembled those of cryptone (V) (Cooke and Macbeth: record $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 226.3 m μ and 314 m μ ; log ϵ , 4.1 and 1.56 respectively).

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